

EXACTNESS OF COMMUTATIVE (IMPLICATIVE) SOFT G-MODULES

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Abstract:

In this paper, we obtain some characterizations for soft sub modules of modules with respect to image, pre image and upper α -inclusion.

Key Words: Soft Set, Soft Homomorphism, Epimorphism, Soft Modules, UP-Module, Partially Ordered Set, Pre Image & Bounded

Introduction:

The notions of ideals in BCK-algebras and positive implicative ideals in BCK-algebras (i.e Iseki implicative ideals) were introduced by Iseki [2]. The notions of commutative (sub-commutative) ideals in BCK-algebras, positive implicative and implicative (Sub-implicative), ideals in BCK-algebras were introduced by [4, 5]. In 1991, Xi [15] applied this concept to BCK-algebras, and he introduced the notion of fuzzy sub - algebras (ideals) of the BCK-algebras. Prabpayak and Leerawat [13, 14] introduced a new algebraic structure which is called KU-algebra. They gave the concept of homomorphisms of KU-algebras and investigated some related properties. Mostafa et al. [9] introduced the notion of sub implicative (sub-commutative) ideals of KU-algebras and investigated of their properties. BCK-algebras form an important class of logical algebras introduced by Iseki [2] and was extensively investigated by several researchers. It is an important way to research the algebras by its ideals. Zadeh [16] introduced the notion of fuzzy sets. At present this concept has been applied to many mathematical branches, such as group, functional analysis, probability theory, topology, and so on. Mostafa et al. [9] introduced the notion of fuzzy KU-ideals of KU-algebras and then they investigated several basic properties which are related to fuzzy KU-ideals. Senapati et al. [7,8] introduced the notion of fuzzy KU-subalgebras (fuzzy KU-ideals) of KU-algebras with respect to a given t-norm, intuitionistic fuzzy bi-normed KU-ideals of a KU-algebra and obtained some of their properties. In this paper, we obtain some characterizations for soft sub modules of a modules with respect to image, pre image and upper α -inclusion.

Basic Definitions and Preliminary Concepts:

In this section, we provide basic definitions and results regarding UP-algebra’s (modules), soft UP-sub modules and UP-module homomorphisms.

Definition 2.1: [UP-algebra]: [A. Lampan]: An algebra $A = (A, \bullet, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is called a UP-algebra, where A is a nonempty set, \bullet is a binary operation on A , and 0 is a fixed element of A (i.e., a nullary operation) if it satisfies the following axioms: for any $x, y, z \in A$,

$$(UP-1): (y \bullet z) \bullet ((x \bullet y) \bullet (x \bullet z)) = 0,$$

$$(UP-2): 0 \bullet x = x,$$

$$(UP-3): x \bullet 0 = 0, \text{ and}$$

(UP-4): $x \bullet y = y \bullet x = 0$ implies $x = y$. From [6], we know that the notion of UP-algebras is a generalization of KUalgebras.

Example 2.2 [A. Lampan]: Let $A = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with a binary operation ‘ \bullet ’ defined by the following Cayley table: \bullet

\bullet	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	0	0
2	0	1	0	3
3	0	1	2	0

Then $(A, \bullet, 0)$ is a UP-algebra. Let $(X, *, 0)$ be an UP-algebra. Then X is a partially ordered set with the following partial ordering \leq defined on X by $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$. X is said to be bounded if there is an element $1 \in X$ such that $x \leq 1$ for all $x \in X$. X is said to be commutative (implicative) if $x \wedge y = y \wedge x$ ($x * (y * x) = x$) for all $x, y \in X$, where $x \wedge y = y * (y * x)$.

Example 2.3: Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ and $*$ be a binary operation on X defined as $x_1 * x_2 = x_1 = \min(x_1, x_2)$ for all $x_1, x_2 \in X$. Then $(X, *, 0)$ forms a commutative UP-algebra.

Definition 2.4: [M. Aslamet. al]: Let M be an UP-algebra. Then by left M -module (abbreviated M -module) we mean an abelian group G with an operation $M \times G \rightarrow G$ with $(m, g) \rightarrow mg$ satisfies the following axioms for all $m, n \in M$ and $g_1, g_2 \in G$;

$$\checkmark \quad (m \wedge n) g_1 = m (ng_1)$$

- ✓ $m(g_1 + g_2) = mg_1 + mg_2$
- ✓ $0g = 0$.

Moreover, if M is bounded and G satisfies $1.g = g$, for all $g \in G$, then G is said to be unitary.

Example 2.5: Any bounded implicative UP-algebra M of a M -module, where ‘+’ is defined as $m + n = (m * n) \vee (n * m)$ and $mn = m \wedge n$. A subgroup N of a M -module G is called sub module of G if N is also a M -module.

Theorem 2.6 [M. Bakhshi]: A subset N of a UP-module G is a UP- sub module of G if and only if $h_1 - h_2 \in H$ and $mh \in H$ for all $h_1, h_2, h \in H$ and $m \in M$.

Definition 2.7 [M. Aslam et. al]: Let G and H be modules over an UP-algebra M . A mapping $F: G \rightarrow H$ is called M -homomorphism if

- ✓ $F(g_1 + g_2) = f(g_1) + f(g_2)$
- ✓ $F(mg) = m f(g)$ for all $g_1, g_2, g \in G$ and $m \in M$.

An UP-module homomorphism is said to be monomorphism (epimorphism) if it is one –one (on to). If it is both one-one and onto, then we say that it is an isomorphism.

Definition 2.8 [Soft set]: A pair (F, A) is called a soft set (S-set) over U , where F is a mapping given by $F: A \rightarrow P(U)$. The pair (F, A) is sometimes called as F_A .

Definition 2.9: A soft set Φ of an UP-module M is said to be a soft UP-submodule if it satisfies

- (SUPM-1) $\Phi(a + b) \geq T \{ \Phi(a), \Phi(b) \}$
- (SUPM-2) $\Phi(-a) = \Phi(a)$ and
- (SUPM-3) $\Phi(xa) \geq \Phi(a)$.

For the sake of simplicity, we shall use the symbols $SS(M)$ and $S(M)$ for the set of all soft sets of M and the set of all soft UP-modules of M , respectively.

Definition 2.10: Let F_A, F_B, F_C be soft UP- modules of $S(M_1), S(M_2)$ and $S(M_3)$ respectively. Then a sequence $F_A^{(\Phi_1, \Phi_1)} \rightarrow F_B^{(\Phi_2, \Phi_2)} \rightarrow F_C$ of $S(M)$ -homomorphism is said to be exact soft UP-module ($S(M)$ -Exact) at F_B if the following conditions are satisfied.

- ✓ $M_1^{(\Phi_1)} \rightarrow M_2^{(\Phi_2)} \rightarrow M_3$ is exact.
- ✓ $A_1^{(\theta_1)} \rightarrow A_2^{(\theta_2)} \rightarrow A_3$ is exact.

Definition 2.11: Let $M=0$ and $A = 0$, then $F_A = 0$. we call F_A is a zero UP-modules.

Theorem 2.12: A soft set $\Phi \in S(M)$ if and only if

- ✓ $\Phi(xa) \geq \Phi(a)$
- ✓ $\Phi(a-b) \geq T \{ \Phi(a), \Phi(b) \}$ for all $a, b \in M$ and $x \in X$.

Definition 2.13: Let $f: M \rightarrow N$ be an UP-module homomorphism and let $\Phi \in SS(M)$ be a soft set on M . Then the image of $f(\Phi)$ of Φ under f is defined as follows

$$f(\Phi)(x) = \begin{cases} \max \Phi(m) & \text{if } f^{-1}(x) \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{if } f^{-1}(x) = \emptyset \end{cases}$$

We shall call $f(\Phi)$ the homomorphic image of Φ under f .

Some Standard Results:

Theorem 3.1: Let $f: M \rightarrow N$ be an UP-module epimorphism and let Φ be a soft sub module of M . Then the homomorphic image $f(\Phi)$ of Φ under f is a soft UP- sub module of N .

Definition 3.2: Let $f: M \rightarrow N$ be a homomorphism of UP-modules and χ a soft set of N . Then the inverse image of χ , $f^{-1}(\chi)$ is a soft set on M given by $f^{-1}(\chi) = \chi(f(m))$ for all $m \in M$.

Theorem 3.3: Let $f: M \rightarrow N$ be a homomorphism of UP-modules and $\chi \in S(N)$, and then the inverse image $f^{-1}(\chi) \in S(M)$.

Theorem 3.4: Let $f: M \rightarrow N$ be an epimorphism of UP-modules. If χ is a soft set on N such that the and the inverse image $f^{-1}(\chi) \in S(M)$, then $\chi \in S(N)$.

Theorem 3.5: For a soft set on M , the following are equivalent;

- ✓ Φ is soft UP-sub module on M .
- ✓ $m_{(\alpha, \beta)}(\Phi)$ is a soft UP-sub module of M for all $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$.

Proof: In this theorem, we have

(i) implies (ii). Now let $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$ be such that $m_{(\alpha, \beta)}(\Phi)$ is a soft sub module on M and let $x \in X, m_1, m_2, m \in M$. Then $\Phi(xm) = m_{\alpha}(\Phi)(xm) \geq m_{\alpha}(\Phi)(m) = \Phi(m) \cdot \alpha$. And since $\alpha \neq 0$ and $\beta \neq 0$, then we have $\Phi(xm) \geq \Phi(m)$.

Now $\Phi(m_1 - m_2) = m_{\alpha}(\Phi)(m_1 - m_2) \geq T \{ m_{\alpha}(\Phi)(m_1), m_{\alpha}(\Phi)(m_2) \} = T \{ \Phi(m_1) \cdot \alpha, \Phi(m_2) \cdot \alpha \} = T \{ \Phi(m_1), \Phi(m_2) \} \cdot \alpha$ which means that $\Phi(m_1 - m_2) \geq T \{ m_{\alpha}(\Phi)(m_1), m_{\alpha}(\Phi)(m_2) \}$.

Hence Φ is soft sub module on M .

Theorem 3.6: Let δ_N and Δ_k be a soft sets over M , where N and k are sub modules of M and χ be a module homomorphism from N to k . If δ_N is soft sub module of M , then so is $\chi(\delta_N)$.

Proof: Let $k_1, k_2 \in K$. Since χ is surjective, there exists $n_1, n_2 \in N$ such that $\chi(n_1) = k_1$ and $\chi(n_2) = k_2$.

Thus $\chi(\delta_N)(k_1-k_2) \geq T \{ \chi(\delta_N)(k_1), \chi(\delta_N)(k_2) \}$ is satisfied.

Now let $r \in R$ and $k \in K$. Since χ is surjective, there exists $n \in N$ such that $\chi(n) = k$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \chi(\delta_N)(rk) &= \cup \{ \delta(x) / n \in N, \chi(n) = rk \} \\ &= \cup \{ \delta(x) / n \in N, \chi n = \chi^{-1}(rk) \} \\ &= \cup \{ \delta(x) / n \in N, i = \chi^{-1}(r\chi(n)) \} \\ &= \cup \{ \delta(x) / n \in N, i = \chi^{-1}(\chi(rn)) = rn \} \\ &= \cup \{ \delta(x) / n \in N, \chi(n) = k \} \\ &\geq \cup \{ \delta(x) / n \in N, \chi(n) = k \} \\ &= \chi(\delta_N)(k) \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\chi(\delta_N)$ is a soft sub module of M .

Theorem 3.7: Let δ_N and Δ_k be a soft sets over M , where N and k are sub modules of M and χ be a module homomorphism from N to k . If Δ_k is soft sub module of M , then so is $\chi^{-1}(\Delta_k)$.

Proof: Let $n_1, n_2 \in N$. Then

$$\chi^{-1}(\Delta_k)(n_1-n_2) \geq T \{ \chi^{-1}(\Delta_k)(n_1), \chi^{-1}(\Delta_k)(n_2) \}$$
 is satisfied.

Now let $r \in R$ and $n \in N$. Then

$$\chi^{-1}(\Delta_k)(rn) = \Delta(\chi(rn)) = \Delta(r\chi(n)) \geq \Delta(\chi(n)) = \chi^{-1}(\Delta_k)(n).$$

Hence $\chi^{-1}(\Delta_k)$ is a soft sub module of M .

Theorem 3.8: If δ_{N_1} is a union soft sub module of M and δ_{N_2} is union sub module of M , then so is $\delta_{N_1} \cup \delta_{N_2}$.

Theorem 3.9: If $\delta_N < M$, then $\delta(0_M) \leq \delta(x)$ for all $x \in N$.

Theorem 3.10: If $\delta_N < M$, then $N_\delta = \{ x \in N / \delta(x) = \delta(0_M) \}$ is a sub module of N .

Theorem 3.11: Let δ_N be a soft set over M and α be a subset of M such that $\delta(0_M) \leq \alpha$. If δ_N is a union soft sub module of M , then $\delta_N(\alpha)$ is a sub module of M .

Definition 3.12: Let N be a sub module of M and δ_N be a soft set over M . Then δ_N is called a union soft sub module of M , denoted by $\delta_N < M$ if

$$(USM-1) \delta(x-y) \leq S \{ \delta(x), \delta(y) \} \text{ and}$$

$$(USM-2) \delta(rx) \leq \delta(x), \text{ for all } x, y \in N \text{ and } r \in R.$$

Example 3.13: Consider the ring $R = (Z_{12}, +, \cdot)$, the left R -module $M = (Z_{12}, +)$ with natural operation and the sub module $N_1 = \{0, 6\}$ of M .

Let the soft δ_N over M where $\delta : N_1 \rightarrow P(M)$ is the set valued function defined by

$$\delta(0) = \{0, 3, 4, 9\} \text{ and } \delta(6) = \{0, 3, 4, 9, 11\}.$$
 Then it can be easily seen that $\delta_{N_1} < M$.

Now, let the submodule of M be $N_2 = \{0, 4, 8\}$ and the soft set Δ_{N_2} over M , where $\Delta : N_2 \rightarrow P(M)$ is a set valued function defined by

$$\Delta(0) = \{0, 3, 9\}, \Delta(4) = \{0, 3, 5, 8, 11\} \text{ and } \Delta(8) = \{0, 3, 5, 8, 9, 11\}.$$
 Then $\Delta(2 \cdot 4) = \Delta(8) = \{0, 3, 5, 8, 9, 11\}$ not less than or equal to $\Delta(4) = \{0, 3, 5, 8, 11\}$. Therefore Δ_{N_2} is not a union soft sub module of M .

Theorem 3.14: Let δ_N be a soft set over M . Then δ_N is a union soft sub module of M if and only if δ_N^r is a soft sub module of M .

Theorem 3.15: Let δ_N and Δ_k be a soft sets over M , where N and K are sub modules of M and χ be a module homomorphism from N to k . If Δ_k is a union soft sub module of M , then so is $\chi^{-1}(\Delta_k)$.

Theorem 3.16: Let δ_N and Δ_k be a soft sets over M , where N and K are sub modules of M and χ be a module isomorphism from N to k . If δ_N is a union soft sub module of M , then so is $\chi^*(\delta_N)$.

Conclusion:

In this paper, we obtain some characterizations for soft sub modules of a modules with respect to image, pre image and upper α -inclusion. Also we provide basic definitions and results regarding UP-algebra's (modules), soft UP-sub modules and UP-module homomorphisms.

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